

X-Ray Diffraction Study of Clay-Humus Complexes

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The nature of interaction products of an illitic soil clay mineral and soil humic compound has been investigated by X-ray diffraction studies. It appears that most of these humus compounds are held on the external surfaces, broken bonds and edges of clay.

IN recent years X-ray diffraction analysis, a nondestructive instrumental technique has been utilised in differentiating between various soil components, viz., (i) clay minerals, (ii) soil humic compounds and (iii) organometallic clay complex. The crystalline clay mineral show characteristic diffraction patterns with a more or less pronounced basal spacing (d_{001}). The diffraction patterns of humic acids usually show broad, diffuse bands near 3.5\AA due to ordering of condensed aromatic layers whereas X-ray patterns of fulvic acids exhibit halos in 4.1 to 4.7\AA regions (γ -bands)¹. Schnitzer *et al*² have reported that adsorption of these two natural degradation products of soil organic matter viz., fulvic and humic acids, alter the X-ray diffraction characteristics, especially, d_{001} spacings of the adsorbed products and are used to indicate the nature of organo-metallic clay complexes at external surface sites and inter-layer spacings. Such studies have their importance in evaluating soil fertility, moisture content and soil aggregation characteristics.

The present work aims to compare X-ray studies of fulvic and humic acid clay complexes with an illitic soil clay mineral.

Materials and Method

Fulvic and humic acids : Fulvic and humic acids were extracted from a humus material existing in a pond sediment (West Bengal) by the Na_2CO_3 extraction procedure as reported earlier by Mukherjee *et al*³ and purified by dialysis and ion-exchange method.

Illitic clay mineral : The clay mineral ($< 1\mu$) used in this investigation was isolated from the same sediment by the dispersion and sedimentation methods described by Piper⁴. The hydrogen clay was prepared from clay suspension by mild acidification and purified by dialysis. Free sesquinosides from soil clays were removed by dithionate method of Mehra and Jackson⁵. From X-ray and chemical analyses, the soil clay mineral was identified as illite. Its

structural composition as obtained from chemical analysis⁶ is

Sodium and calcium clays : Na and Ca saturated clays were prepared by repeated treatment of the colloidal hydrogen clay fractions with respective chloride solutions and decantation of equilibrium solution. The samples were washed with alcohol and vacuum dried at room temperature.

Preparation of organo-clay complexes : Purified fulvic and humic acids were separately mixed with H-clay (original), oxide-free H-clay, Na-H-clay and Ca-H-clay in different molar ratios (determined from electrometric titrations⁷). The mixtures were allowed to equilibrate for 7-8 days and then each of these mixtures were centrifuged at 2500 r.p.m. The equilibrium solutions were decanted. The residual samples were finally washed with alcohol, vacuum dried at room temperature and subjected to X-ray diffraction analysis (Philips 1010 unit with 11.54 cm Debye Scherrer Camera, with CuK_α radiation).

Results and Discussion

The diffraction patterns of the clay mineral (in original H-clay material as well as in oxide-free clay fractions) and various organo-clay complexes are presented in Tables (1 to 3).

Table 1 shows the X-ray diffraction characteristics of an illitic clay mineral isolated from a pond sediment. The basal reflections in original H-clay and oxide free H-clay samples are slightly different (9.60\AA and 9.64\AA). The d_{001} reflections in both cases are of weak intensity due to small particle size ($< 1\mu$).

Table 2 shows the effect of higher mol. ratios of H-clay/F. A. complexes on lattice spacings. d_{001} spacings changed from 9.7Å to 10.1Å with increasing mol. ratios from 1 : 12 to 1 : 36. On removal of free sesquioxides from H-clay fraction and subsequent interaction with fulvic acids, d_{001} spacings are found to be slightly changed (9.9Å to 9.93Å). This shows that adsorption of a large number of organic molecules increases d_{001} spacings to a lower order. It

may be inferred that adsorption of F. A. on clay surfaces occur mostly on external surfaces, broken edges and bonds of the crystallites.

Table 3 represents the diffraction patterns of H-clay-humic acid interaction products : d_{001} spacings increased from 9.77Å to 9.93Å with mol. ratios 1 : 5 to 1 : 40 respectively. With oxide free clay d_{001} values change slightly from 9.7Å to 9.77Å.

TABLE—1 X-RAYS DIFFRACTION OF ORIGINAL CLAY, OXIDE-FREE CLAY, Na-H-CLAY AND Ca-H-CLAY LATTIC SPACINGS IN Å AND ESTIMATED INTENSITIES OF LINES

Original Clay		Oxide-Free Clay		Na-H-Clay		Ca-H-Clay	
d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I
9.60	M(B)	9.64	M(B)	9.92	VW	9.92	VW
7.05	VW	7.12	VVW	7.19	VVW	7.18	VVW
4.42	VVW	4.43	VVW	4.49	VS	4.47	W(B)
3.32	W	3.34	W	4.16	W	4.15	W
				3.51	VVW	4.27	VVW
2.49	M(B)	2.50	W(B)	3.34	VS	3.34	MS
1.80	VVW	1.80	VVW	3.02	VW	3.01	VW
				2.58	W(B)	2.57	MS(B)
1.53	VVW	1.52	VVW	1.82	VW	1.81	VVW
				1.506	VW(B)	1.49	VVW

TABLE—2 X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERNS OF ORIGINAL OXIDE-FREE CLAY-FA COMPLEXES

Original Clay : FA Complexes in Different Mol. Ratios						Oxide-Free Clay : FA Complexes in Different mol. Ratios							
1 : 12		1 : 16		1 : 24		1 : 36		1 : 40		1 : 52.5		1 : 60	
d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I
9.77	MS	9.80	W	9.92	MS	10.10	MS	9.90	MS(B)	9.92	MS(B)	9.93	MS(B)
9.69	W(B)	9.69	MW	9.69	MW(B)	9.69	VW(B)	9.70	VVW	9.70	VVW	9.71	VW
4.45	S	4.46	MS	4.46	S	4.48	MS	4.49	MS	4.49	W	4.49	W(B)
3.35	W(B)	3.30	VW	3.30	VW	3.30	VVW	3.36	W(B)	3.35	VW	3.35	W(B)
2.55	MW	2.55	MW(B)	2.55	VVW	2.55	W(B)	2.56	VVW	2.55	VW	2.55	W(B)
1.49	MW(B)	1.49	MW	1.49	W(B)	1.49	W(B)	1.50	MW	1.50	VVW	1.50	VW

TABLE—3 X-RAYS DIFFRACTION PATTERNS OF ORIGINAL CLAY/OXIDE-FREE CLAY-HA COMPLEXES

Original Clay-H.A. Complexes in Different Mol. Ratios						Oxide-Free Clay-H.A. Complexes in Different Mol. Ratios							
1 : 15		1 : 12.5		1 : 25		1 : 40		1 : 5		1 : 37 : 2		1 : 42.5	
d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I	d, in Å	I
9.77	MS	9.80	MS	9.92	MS	9.93	MS	9.70	MS(B)	9.73	MS(B)	9.77	MS(B)
7.10	W	7.10	W	7.13	W	7.14	VVW	7.14	VVW	7.14	VVW	7.14	VVW
4.96	W	4.85	W	4.94	W	4.94	W	4.47	S(B)	4.47	S(B)	4.47	S(B)
4.47	VVS	4.46	VVS	4.49	VVS	4.49	VVS	4.30	VW	4.30	VW	4.31	VW
3.89	VW	3.89	VW	4.27	VW	4.27	VW	3.45	VW	3.45	VW	3.46	VW
3.71	VVW	3.70	VVW	3.89	VVW	3.89	VVW	2.57	MB	2.57	MB	2.57	MB
3.51	VVW	3.70	VVW	3.39	VVW	3.69	VW	1.81	VW	1.81	VW	1.81	VW
3.33	VS	3.31	VS	3.51	VS	3.52	VW	1.50	MB	1.50	MB	1.50	MB
3.19	VW	3.21	VW	3.34	VW	3.34	VW						
2.98	VW	2.89	VW	3.21	VW	3.21	VW						
2.85	VS	2.85	VW	3.12	VS	3.12	VW						
3.57	W	2.60	W	2.99	W	3.01	W						
2.45	W	2.60	W	2.86	W	2.86	W						
2.39	W	2.39	W	2.88	W	2.76	W						
1.97	W	2.12	W	2.57	W	2.66	W						
1.81	W	1.81	W	1.82	W	1.82	W						
1.69	W	1.67	W	1.67	W	1.66	W						
1.65	W	1.63	W	1.62	W	1.63	W						
1.50	W	1.49	W	1.49	W	1.50	W						

*S = Strong, MS = Medium strong, S(B) = Strong (broad), VS = Very strong, W = Weak, MW = Medium weak, VVS = Very very strong, VVW = Very very weak, VW = Very weak, W(B) = Weak broad, M(B) = Medium broad, MS(B) = Medium Strong (broad), I = Intensity of the diffraction patterns, d = Basal spacings in Å.

Tables 4 and 5 show the effect of exchangeable cations Na⁺ and Ca⁺⁺ (monovalent and divalent ions) on d₀₀₁ spacings of clay humus complexes. The d₀₀₁ spacings (Table 4 of Na-clay F. A. complexes were 9.9Å to 10.24Å with moderately strong intensity. The increase in basal spacings indicate that Na atom acts as a bridge between clay-Na-F.A. molecule. Similar observations are

observed with clay-Na-H.A. complexes.

Table 5 represents the effect of calcium on clay-humus interaction products. The d₀₀₁ values of Ca-clay-F. A. complexes are 9.92Å to 10.1Å with mol. ratios 1 : 10 to 1 : 55. The d₀₀₁ values of Ca-clay- H. A. complexes 9.92 to 9.94Å with mol. ratios 1 : 10 to 1 : 90.

TABLE—4 X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERNS OF Na-H-CLAY-FA/HA COMPLEXES

Na-H-Clay F. A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios						Na-H-Clay H. A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios					
1 : 25		1 : 40		1 : 95		1 : 10		1 : 30		1 : 55	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
9.90	MS	10.10	MS	10.24	MS	9.92	MW	10.10	MW	10.18	MW
7.06	VVW	7.06	VVW	7.07	MS	7.07	VVW	7.07	VVW	7.07	VVW
5.96	VVW	5.96	VVW	6.96	VVW	5.97	S	5.98	S	5.98	S
5.70	VVW	5.70	VVW	5.70	VVW	5.71	W	5.71	VW	5.71	W
4.47	W	4.47	S	4.47	S	4.47	MS	4.47	W	4.47	VW
4.32	VVW	4.32	VW	4.32	VW	4.33	VW	4.33	VW	4.38	VW
4.27	W	4.28	VW	4.27	VVW	4.28	VW	4.27	VW	4.28	W
4.12	VVW	4.12	VVW	4.12	VVW	4.13	MS	4.13	MS	4.13	MS
3.86	VW	3.86	VW	3.86	VVW	3.85	VW	3.85	W	3.85	VVW
3.68	VW	3.68	VW	3.68	VW	3.68	VW	3.68	VW	3.68	VW
3.51	MW	3.51	MW	3.51	MW	3.51	MW	3.51	MW	3.51	MW
3.34	MS	3.34	MS	3.34	MS	3.34	MS	3.34	MS	3.34	MS
3.20	W	3.20	W	3.20	W	3.20	W	3.20	W	3.20	W
3.00	VW	3.00	VW	3.00	VW	3.00	MS	3.00	MS	3.00	MS
2.97	W	2.97	VW	2.98	VW	2.98	VW	2.98	W	2.98	VW
2.84	VW	2.84	VW	2.84	W(B)	2.84	W	2.84	VW(B)	2.84	VW(B)
2.58	M(B)	2.55	MS(B)	2.58	W(B)	2.56	VW(B)	2.58	W(B)	2.56	VW
2.45	VW	2.46	VW	2.46	VW(B)	2.46	VVW	2.46	VVW	2.46	VVW
2.38	MW	2.38	VW	2.38	W	2.38	VVW	2.38	VVW	2.38	VVW
2.13	W	2.13	VVW	2.13	W(B)	2.13	VVW	2.13	VVW	2.13	VVW
1.99	W(B)	1.98	W(B)	1.98	VW	1.99	VVW	1.99	VVW	1.99	VVW
1.81	VVW	1.81	VVW	1.81	VVW	1.81	VVW	1.81	VVW	1.81	VW
1.69	W(B)	1.68	VVW	1.68	VW	1.68	VVW	1.68	VVW	1.68	VVW
1.65	W(B)	1.65	VVW	1.65	W	1.65	V(B)	1.65	V(B)	1.65	VW
1.50	M(B)	1.49	W(B)	1.50	MS(B)	1.50	VVW	1.50	VVM	1.50	W

TABLE—5 X-RAY DIFFRACTION PATTERNS OF CA-H-CLAY-F.A./H.A. COMPLEXES

Ca-H-Clay-F.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios						Ca-H-Clay-H.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios					
1 : 10		1 : 30		1 : 55		1 : 10		1 : 35		1 : 90	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
9.92	MW	9.93	MW	10.10	MW	9.92	MS	9.93	MS	9.94	MS
7.62	VVW	7.64	VVW	7.67	W	7.67	VVW	7.67	VVW	7.67	VVW
7.18	VVW	7.18	VVW	7.18	VVW	7.18	VW	7.18	VW	7.18	VW
6.03	VVW	6.02	VVW	6.02	VW	6.02	VW	6.02	VW	6.02	VW
4.90	VVW	4.90	VW	4.90	VW	4.90	VVW	4.90	VVW	4.90	VVW
4.47	W(B)	4.47	W(B)	4.49	S	4.47	VS	4.80	VS	4.49	VW
4.27	VVW	4.26	VVW	4.27	MS	4.27	MW	4.27	VW	4.27	W
4.12	VVW	4.12	VVW	4.12	VVW	4.12	MW	4.12	VVW	4.12	VVW
3.85	W	3.85	W	3.86	W	3.86	VW	3.86	VW	3.86	VW
3.68	W	3.68	W	3.68	W	3.72	VW	3.72	VW	3.72	VW
3.51	VVW	3.51	VVW	3.51	MW	3.50	VW	3.50	VW	3.41	W
3.34	W(B)	3.34	VW(B)	3.34	S	3.36	MS	3.36	MS	3.36	MS
3.20	VVW	3.21	VVW	3.21	VW	3.21	VVW	3.21	VVW	3.21	VVW
3.06	VVW	3.06	VVW	3.06	VVW	3.16	S	3.16	S	3.16	S
3.00	VVW	3.00	VVW	3.00	W	3.13	VVW	3.13	VVW	3.13	VW
2.87	VW	2.87	VVW	2.87	W	2.87	VVW	2.87	VVW	2.87	VVW
2.80	VVW	2.80	VVW	2.80	VVW	2.99	VVW	2.99	VVW	2.99	VVW
2.55	W(B)	2.58	VW(B)	2.57	S	2.57	MW(B)	2.59	W	2.58	MS(B)
2.46	VVW	2.46	VVW	2.46	VW	2.46	VW	2.46	VW	2.46	VVW
2.38	VVW	2.38	VVW	2.38	W	2.36	VW	2.36	VW	2.38	VW
2.28	VW	2.28	VVW	2.28	VW	2.29	VVW	2.29	VVW	2.29	VVW
2.24	VVW	2.24	VVW	2.24	VVW	2.26	VVW	2.26	VVW	2.26	VVW
2.13	VVW	2.13	VVW	2.13	MW	2.13	VVW	2.13	VVW	2.13	VVW
1.98	VW	1.98	VVW	1.98	W	1.98	VW	1.98	VVW	1.98	VVW
1.84	VVW	1.84	VVW	1.82	WB	1.82	VW	1.98	VW	1.82	VW
1.71	VVW	1.71	VVW	1.71	VVW	1.71	VVW	1.71	W(B)	1.70	VW
1.65	VVW	1.62	VVW	1.65	VW	1.64	VVW	1.64	VW	1.64	VVW
1.52	VVW	1.52	VW	1.52	VW	1.50	VW	1.50	VW	1.50	VW
1.49	VVW	1.49	VVW	1.50	MS	1.49	VW(B)	1.51	W(B)	1.49	M(B)

Tables 6 and 7 show the effect of variation of pH on interaction and on the d_{001} spacings of different clay-F. A./H.A. combinations. With increasing mol. ratios, pH of FA/HA clay complexes decrease. It appears that the degree of ionisation of functional groups namely, phenolic, carboxylic groups in FA/HA clay complexes decrease. It appears that the

the magnitude and nature of adsorption on clay surface have effect on d_{001} spacings. At pH < 4.0 few of acid functional groups are ionised and FA/HA behave as natural molecules that may have penetrated lattice spacings of the clay species, resulting in the shifting of basal spacings. At pH > 4.0, the ionisation of the functional groups increase rapidly due to which basal spacings decrease.

TABLE—6 EFFECT OF pH ON d_{001} SPACING OF CLAY MINERAL AND CLAY-H.A./F.A. COMPLEXES

Samples	pH	d_{001} , Å	Intensity (I)
Original Clay	4.05	9.62	MS
Oxide-Free Clay	4.20	9.64	MS
ORIGINAL CLAY-F. A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 12	3.45	9.77	MS
1 : 16	4.0	9.80	W
1 : 24	3.5	9.92	VW
1 : 36	3.0	10.10	MS
OXIDE-FREE CLAY-F.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 40	4.5	9.90	W
1 : 52.5	4.0	9.92	M(B)
1 : 60	3.5	9.93	MS
ORIGINAL CLAY-H.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 5	4.5	9.77	MS
1 : 12.5	4.0	9.80	MW
1 : 25	3.5	9.92	M(B)
1 : 40	3.0	9.93	M(B)
OXIDE-FREE CLAY-H.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 5	4.5	9.70	M(W)
1 : 37.2	4.0	9.73	W(B)
1 : 42.5	3.5	9.77	W(B)

TABLE—7 EFFECT OF pH ON d_{001} SPACING OF Na/Ca-H-CLAY AND THEIR DIFFERENT COMPLEXES WITH ORGANIC MATTER FRACTIONS

Samples	pH	d_{001} , Å	Intensity (I)
Na-Clay	6.7	9.92	VW
Ca-Clay	6.9	9.92	W(B)
NA-CLAY : F.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 25	6.9	9.90	W
1 : 70	6.5	10.10	MW
1 : 95	5.8	10.28	MS
NA-CLAY : H.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 10	6.5	9.92	VW
1 : 30	6.0	10.10	W(B)
1 : 50	5.5	10.18	MW
CA-CLAY : F.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 10	7.0	9.92	W(B)
1 : 30	6.5	9.926	W(B)
1 : 55	6.0	10.10	MW
CA-CLAY : H.A. Complexes in Different Mole Ratios			
1 : 10	7.0	9.92	W
1 : 35	6.5	9.93	MS
1 : 90	6.0	9.94	W

degree of ionisation of functional groups namely, phenolic, carboxylic groups in FA/HA is related to

Na-clay-FA interaction products show their pH (5.8 to 6.9) and the d_{001} spacings of these products are (9.92 to 10.28 Å). Similar observations are made for Na-clay-HA complexes d_{001} (9.92 to 10.18 Å). In Ca-clay-FA-complexes pH increase from 6.0 to 7.0 and the d_{001} spacings of such products alter from 9.92 to 10.1 Å. With Ca-clay-HA complexes pH change from 6.0 to 7.0, d_{001} spacings alter slightly. Such changes in d_{001} spacings with different Na/Ca-clay-FA/HA complexes might be due to small specific adsorption or ligand exchange reaction. The alteration of d_{001} spacings with higher mol. ratios of FA/HA to the clay mineral species taken in this investigation is relatively low in comparison to that reported for products with montmorillonite group mineral (Schnitzer²). It is inferred that inter-planar swelling of a non-expanding mineral, taken in this investigation, is of low order, since the mineral has lower charge density (-0.11) with smaller inter-layer surface. It appears from this study that most of FA/HA molecules are held on external surfaces, broken bonds and edges.

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